

Post drought recovery strategy among pastoral households using effective copying mechanisms in Harshin Woreda, Somali regional state, Ethiopia: A Study

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Abstract

Pastoralists are nature lovers and their livelihood mainly depends upon the products and productivity of domestic animals like cattle, camels, goats, sheep, and donkeys etc. The pastoralist does not exist either individually or in a homogenous group. The lonely herder wandering in the wilderness to find pasture and water for animals is a romanticized picture of the harsh living and survival conditions of pastoralists (Justin Ginnetti and Travis Franck, 2014). Rather, pastoralists exist as individuals in communities that are often tribally affiliated, with partly different histories, different languages, and social and cultural values and ties, distinct struggles for power. They may have diverse species of livestock, with different degrees of mobility and follow different mobility routes. They may be more or less diversified and commercialized and with different levels of access to resources and markets as well as different views of themselves and their future.(Justin Ginnetti and Travis Franck , 2014).It is estimated that around 180 million pastoralists are living in developing country including in Sub-Saharan Africa. Out of 180 million, it is estimated that around (50million) live in the Sub-Sahara rangelands of Africa in general and East Africa in particularly. According to study about 12% of the rural populations (Thorntonetal,2002) are pastoralists and their livelihoods depend upon livestock production and productivity. An essential part of their survival strategy involves taking advantage of the mixed social environment that many pastoralists live in through trading, exchanging, or allying with neighboring groups such as foragers, farmers, urban dwellers and sometimes other pastoral people (Fratkin,2007). Recurrent droughts, among other factors, have deteriorated the ecosystem, eroded livelihood assets of pastoralists and thereby jeopardized livelihoods of the pastoralists where Harshin Woreda is not exceptional. Therefore, this study was carried out to assess the post drought recovery strategies adapted by the pastoralists in Harshin Woreda, Somali Region in Ethiopia.

Introduction

Pastoralists are nature lovers and their livelihood mainly depends upon the products and productivity of domestic animals like cattle, camels, goats, sheep, and donkeys etc. The pastoralist does not exist either individually or in a homogenous group. The lonely herder wandering in the wilderness to find pasture and water for animals is a romanticized picture of the harsh living and survival conditions of pastoralists (Justin Ginnetti and Travis Franck, 2014). Rather, pastoralists exist as individuals in communities that are often tribally affiliated, with partly different histories, different languages, and social and cultural values and ties, distinct struggles for power. They may have diverse species of livestock, with different degrees of mobility and follow different mobility routes. They may be more or less diversified and commercialized and with different levels of access to resources and markets as well as different views of themselves and their future.(Justin Ginnetti and Travis Franck , 2014)

It is estimated that around 180 million pastoralists are living in developing country including in Sub-Saharan Africa. Out of 180 million, it is estimated that around (50million) live in the Sub-Sahara rangelands of Africa in general and East Africa in particularly. According to study about 12% of the rural populations (Thorntonetal. 2002) are pastoralists and their livelihoods depend upon livestock production and productivity. An essential part of their survival strategy involves taking advantage of the mixed social environment that many pastoralists live in through trading, exchanging, or allying with neighboring groups such as foragers, farmers, urban dwellers and sometimes other pastoral people (Fratkin, 2007). They typically live and graze their animals in marginal areas that are too cold, high, or dry for traditional crop agriculture. In Ethiopia, livestock is one of the major agricultural sub-sectors and generates 12% of the national gross domestic products (MoFED, 2012). In addition, livestock plays an important role for welfare at the household level by providing services. Pastoralism and pastoral production systems support 100–200 million people globally and covers 41% of the Earth surface (Birch and Grahn, 2007). This production system world over has evolved in dryland areas of the planet, which constitute some of the harshest and remotest places on earth (Oxfam, 2002). In these environments, rainfall can be anywhere from 25mm to 600mm, often varying as much in time and place as in quantity. Given this aridity, it is hardly surprising that pastoralists are subject to higher levels of risk than those

living in areas where farming is a viable option. The infrastructure in these areas is almost entirely unknown (or almost entirely dilapidated). Nevertheless, there is a considerable body of evidence that pastoralists have well-designed risk-management and adaptation strategies (Birch and Grahn, 2007). Most of the available studies on pastoralism in Ethiopia estimate that pastoral and agro-pastoral communities in Ethiopia constitute roughly 10- 12% of the total population. According to these studies, these groups occupy some 60% the country's land mass, mainly the peripheral areas of the country. The main pastoral communities are the Somali (53%), Afar (29%) and Borena (10%) living in the Southeast, Northeastern and Southern parts of Ethiopia, respectively, and the balance (8%) are found in Southern, Gambella and Benshangul regions (Coppock 1994; Hogg 1997b; Sandford and Yohannes 2000). The majority of these are pastoralists engaged in extensive livestock herding. Within and between each of these groups there are different adaptive specializations dependent on varying ecological, economic and cultural factors.

The Somali region is one of the regions with large number of pastoral and agro-pastoral community. The region in general and Harshin district in particular have seriously suffered from recurrent droughts. Added to the harsh environment, the Harshin woreda pastoralists have been the frontline victims of recurrent droughts (Francois,2019). To say some, the scare of the drought in the year 2000 was not completely healed, when it was again heated in 2003. This zone was one of the most seriously affected areas in the country in 2003. Subsequently in the recent past also Ethiopia suffered two distinct droughts which affected different geographical areas, first the El Niño-type drought in 2015-16, followed immediately by the Indian Ocean Dipole (or IOD associated drought) in 2016-17.(Francois,2019).

Recurrent droughts, among other factors, have deteriorated the ecosystem, eroded livelihood assets of pastoralists and thereby jeopardized livelihoods of the pastoralists in this district. Nevertheless, the pastoralists have never been passive victims of drought. They have been developing local adaptive strategies to the changing environmental conditions. Their long-established indigenous mechanisms or strategies are facing a formidable challenge with the high pace of change in the environment. Therefore, there is a need to understand their coping and recovery strategies in order to make development initiatives in these areas.

Issues

Drought is one of the most inhibiting factors in pastoral production systems in the horn of Africa. It has had important implications on the predicaments of pastoral households and their responses to its various phases. Although there is a growing and influential body of literature concerning failure of development interventions, conflict management, drought occurrences, early warning systems, drought coping strategies, little attempt has been given particularly to post-drought recovery strategies of pastoral households. Most of the studies carried out on drought and drought management in pastoral areas of the region under consideration have not been extended beyond such issues as short-term impacts and coping mechanisms. The available literature is particularly limited on the transition from drought to post-drought period as well as on the prevailing situation in the post-drought phase. There is little information on the post-drought period in general and on the recovery strategies in particular. Practices of pastoralists as well as experiences of external agents in the post-drought period have not been adequately researched and documented. Strengthening and rebuilding of appropriate post-drought recovery strategies, therefore, need further studies.

Research Questions:-

The Critical questions that this researcher sought to explore as follows:-

- What are the effects of drought on the pastoral livelihoods in Harshin district?
- What are the post drought recovery Strategies adapted by the community?
- How do external agents or stakeholders in the study area influence the community coping mechanisms and recovery strategies in the post drought period?
- What are the key policy issues that need to be strengthened /addressed to reduce vulnerability to drought among pastoralist communities?

Research Objectives

General Objective:-

The general objective of the research was to assess how the pastoralists' community in drought prone areas of Degahbour district rebuild and strengthen their recovery strategies in the post drought period.

Specific Objectives:

- To assess the effect of drought on pastoral areas and the livelihoods of the pastoralists.
- To assess the post drought recovery mechanisms among the pastoral community in the study area.
- To assess the role of external agents/stakeholders in influencing the pastoralists recovery especially in the post drought period.
- To identify key policy issues that needs to be strengthened or addressed to make pastoralists less vulnerable to drought.

Significance of the Study

The information generated by this study will be useful for Local Administrators, Regional and National governments of Ethiopia, as well as local NGOs and international NGOs to have an in-depth understanding about the importance of post drought recovery strategies of the pastoralists and appropriate interventions to mitigate drought impacts in pastoral areas. This would, in turn, help to formulate and implement effective measures and adjustments of post drought recovery strategies early to improve pastoralists' production systems and thereby their contributions towards the Somali Region's economic development. The findings of this study will also help to inform readers, academics and researchers to understand better these issues and subject and it will also help policy makers for making effective policies and programs in this regards.

Conceptual Framework for Drought Management in Pastoral Areas

Given constant levels of hazards over time, adaptation will allow a system to reduce the risk associated with these hazards by reducing its social vulnerability. Faced with increased hazards, a system may maintain current levels of risk through such adaptation. If hazards increase dramatically in frequency or severity, a human system may face greater risk despite reduction in social vulnerability achieved through the implementation of adaptation strategies. The direct effect of adaptation is therefore to reduce social vulnerability.

A conceptual framework is made below (**See Figure 1**) in order to inform a drought management system, adapted to a pastoral context is presented in. This includes a distinction

between *mitigation activities* to minimize the impact of drought on production systems and livelihoods, and *relief activities* for the welfare of those rendered destitute. Often, and ideally, mitigation activities can be triggered by early warning and contingency planning during the onset of drought, while relief is generally more appropriate at a later stage.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework for Drought management

Literature Review

Concepts and Definitions of key Terms

Pastoralism

Pastoralism is an economic pattern in which people make their living by tending herds of large animals. And it is most often an adaptation to semi-arid open countries in which farming cannot

be easily sustained (Daniel, 2005) .As a broad description, pure pastoralist household normally receives at least 80% of its cash income through the sale of livestock and their products, and consumes at least 30 % of its food intake in the form of meat, milk products, or blood (Future Agriculture, 2007)

According to UNDP 2003, Pastoralism is an economic system in which most household gain more than 50 percent of total gross household income (i.e. including the value of products produced and consumed within the household) from livestock related activities, using unimproved pasture. And systems where more than 25 percent of income comes from livestock, more than 50 percent from cropping is labeled as agro-Pastoralism.

Pastoral coping and adaptive strategies

Coping mechanisms are responses of an individual group or society to challenging situations. The coping mechanisms lie within the frame work of the individual's, group's or society's risk aversion or tolerance level, i.e are institutes to minimize risk or to manage loss. While some coping mechanisms may be brought into play by stress factors, others may be an intensification of an already in- built strategy.

Coping strategies are bundle of people's responses to declining food availability and entitlements in abnormal seasons or years. Coping is thus defined as a short-term response to an immediate and in-habitual decline in access to food, and means acting to survive (Fassil *et al*, 2001). Coping strategies are characteristically "emergency responses" or "fall-back mechanisms" of people in normally secure livelihood systems that are experiencing abnormal risk.

Households confronted with a livelihood shock that undermines their access to food can react in a number of ways. During the 1980s and 1990s, an extensive literature on coping strategies, usually in the context of drought in sub Saharan Africa and South Asia, concluded that these responses can be categorized as “protect consumption” and “modify consumption” (Deveruex,2006). Protecting consumption requires buying or being given food to maintain food intake levels. Modifying consumption includes reducing or diversifying consumption or reducing consumers by migrating or sending some household members elsewhere.

To respond to the harsh climatic realities of the low lands, pastoralists have evolved a variety of coping strategies. These have been generally successful, but within the last twenty years, drought, which had historically occurred every ten years and have occurred every three, two years, placing untenable demands on traditional ways of avoiding disaster.

Pastoral coping strategies can be grouped broadly as either managerial strategies or community strategies. Managerial strategies include movement and migration; Various aspects of herd management; supplementation of grazing with other feeds; changes in herding labor with intensification of stress; managements of diseases (both human and livestock); and changes in human diet. Community strategies include; sharing, lending and giving of livestock as gifts and institution of legal restrictions, on the rangeland resources (Deucher, 2005)

The frequency of adoption of different coping strategies provides an indication of the sequence in which they are adopted. As general rule, strategies that are the least costly (both economically and socially) and are most easily reversible are adopted first, as an immediate response to food shock. Example includes mild rationing of food consumption, or reducing non-essential spending. Strategies that are most damaging to livelihoods or social status, and most difficult to reverse, are adopted last, after all other survival strategies have been exhausted. Examples include: Selling farm lands, or begging, or engaging in illegal activities.

Adaptive strategies can be seen as an expression of negotiated decisions for individual and community livelihoods, among members of households and communities, as traditional systems are influenced by such factors as the socio-economic and ecological environments, and contemporary knowledge systems (including science and technology). Adaptive strategies are distinct from coping strategies in that they represent a permanent mix of productive activities and require the modification of community rules and institutions to meet livelihood needs. They are most observable in vulnerable socio-economic systems and modes of production.

Impact of Droughts

Pastoral community have suffered a series of livelihood shocks in recent years, some natural (Drought and livestock diseases), others political (a crackdown on contraband trade, bans by

Gulf states on livestock imports, violent conflict between clans and or sub clans or others (Deveruex, 2006) Of all the natural hazards, droughts are potentially those having the greatest economic impact and affecting the greatest number of people. Earthquake and cyclones may be of enormous physical intensity but are invariably of short duration and geographically limited. By contrast droughts affect large geographical areas, often covering whole countries or parts of continents and may last for several months and in some cases several years (Astrid, 1999),

Impacts of drought in the pastoral sector can be discussed by dividing the drought period into three phases. Levels of and trends in pasture production, livestock numbers and productivity, cereal availability and relative prices all constrain what can be achieved within each phase as is shown below (Scoones, 1994)

In phase one, drought brings about a fall in available forage throughout the system. it is assumed here that drought conditions are sufficiently harsh and widespread for extensive movement to be able to compensate for falling fodder availability. Livestock numbers start to fall, through sales and deaths among the most vulnerable(see Table 1). However, despite animal losses, there remains an overall imbalance between livestock numbers and available fodder. As drought hits harder, bringing failure of cereal harvests and deteriorating animal condition, grain prices rise while livestock prices fall.

In phase two, herd numbers continue to fall, as sales and deaths continue, despite the leveling off and gradual improvement in fodder availability. Shortage of grain continue to keep food prices high, although these levels will be somewhat moderate where food aid is delivered in substantial quantitative. In phase three with improved rainfall, fodder production starts to recover; yet livestock numbers remain well below the level, which could make effective use of available, grazing (Scoones ,1994)

Table.1.Livestock loss during drought in pastoral regions

Drought Year	Regions	Affected livestock species (%)				
		Cattle	Sheep	Goat	Equines	Camel
1972/1974	Afar	72	45	34	-	37
1983/1985	Oromia					
	Borana	60	-	-	-	-
1995/1997	Oromia					
	Borana	78	-	-	-	45
1999/2000	Afar	Up to 45	Up to 15	Up to 15	-	Up to 25
"	Oromia					
	Bale	50	35	20	20	15
"	Somali	Up to 80	60	40	-	35
"	South Omo	50	20	20	-	15

Source: Poverty Reduction Strategy and Pastoral Development 2001

Contextual Changes and Specific Crisis Dynamics

Although the crises in 2011-12 and 2016-17 were labeled droughts, it would be misleading to think of them simply as the consequences of rain failure. The interaction between rain shortage, mobility, political crises and conflicts has been widely documented. Throughout the region, the worst indicators were not necessarily in the areas with the greatest anomalies in rainfall, but rather in the areas that had been affected by conflict, or were marginalized and under-developed (Francois et.al.,2019). In pastoral or agro-pastoral areas, one failed rainy season should only create hardship rather than famine. On the other hand, if several consecutive bad seasons are combined with structural poverty, political marginalization or conflict, the population may be unable to adopt adaptive population movements and coping mechanisms. Climate change is increasingly affecting the area, with changing rainfall patterns (both in terms of time and geography) and the modification of the vegetation cover. As a result, periods between bad years are becoming shorter and recovery is more difficult (Francois et.al.,2019).

Levels of Resources Allocated

Between 2011-12 and 2016-17, there was no significant difference in the amount mobilized for the global international response for Somalia, while the amount was somewhat higher for Ethiopia. For

Kenya, very little was mobilized in both cases by ECHO, while resources coming from EU funded development programmes were allocated to the drought response. It seems that the main question is not how much money is mobilized but how it is used. (Francois et.al.,2019))

Understanding weather information better and using it more efficiently.

Although weather forecasting is continually improving and becoming more accessible, it is still not playing a significant role in determining how resources should be used. Governments, who have access to the information, are still rarely willing to allocate resources on the basis of forecasts, when they have so many other pressing demands for resources. Unfortunately, the general unwillingness to act on the basis of forecasts is extended, to a certain degree, to preparedness measures. The implications of the unwillingness to allocate resources until indicators of suffering are rising are well recognized given the time taken to translate funding decisions to assistance on the ground, response will always be late((Francois et.al.,2019)).

Timelines of the Response

There was a significant improvement in terms of alertness and geographic coverage between 2011 and 2016-17, with some variation between the three countries. The quicker triggering of the response in Somalia in 2016, and even more in 2017, was possible due to robust early warning information which was provided more quickly through different formal and informal channels, the presence of more actors in the field and the engagement of key donors who were determined to avoid a repetition of the 2011 famine. In Kenya and Ethiopia, the improvement in timeliness was more limited as most of the early warning systems and response mechanisms are government-led systems which too often react slowly. ((Francois et.al.,2019))

Research Methodology

Study Area

Harshin District(Woreda) is one of the eleven district of Fafen Zone in the northern part of The Ethiopia Somali Regional State. The woreda is located and bounded between 8° 27' 11.0187" N to 10° 01' 40.170 North and "N" and 41° 40'13.6557" E to 45° 32' 35.7129" East. It covers a total

area of 1,315.1 km² and is bordered by Kebribayah woreda in the west, Somaliland to the north, east, and Aware and Degahbur woredas to the east and south respectively. Harshin town is about 120 km from Jigjiga.(CSA ,(2007)

Source: www.maplandia.com

Fig 2. Map of the Study Area

Demography:

Based on the 2007 Census conducted by the Central Statistical Agency of Ethiopia (CSA), this woreda has a total population of 80,244, of whom 43,869 are men and 36,375 women. While 8,226 or 10.25% are urban inhabitants, a further 39,275 or 48.95% are pastoralists. 99.39% of the population said they were Muslim (CSA (2007) .This woreda is primarily inhabited by the Sacad Muuse sub-clan of the Habr Awal(UNDP)Emergencies Unit for Ethiopia report, dated 30 May 1998)

Research Design

The study adopted descriptive research design. The descriptive research design selected with the assumption that will be helpful to obtain relevant information from concerned respondents on the, assessing the adaptive strategy of pastoralist to recurrent drought in Harshin woreda in Somali regional state and to gain detailed data from large number of respondents to draw the necessary conclusion

Sample size Sampling Method

In this study Harshin woredas was selected purposively, out of twenty one kebeles only three kebeles namely Lankeyrta, Farah liban and Aran'are randomly selected and using Yamane (1967) total sample size (175) selected and proportionately distributed among kebeles.

Data Analysis Method

Datas so collected were edited, coded-decoded , tabulated , processed for analyses using statistical tools accordingly inferences are drawn conclusion and recommendations are made.

Results and Discussion

Sources of Income

Sources of income are very important not only for a particular society but also individual. Income sources indicate the level of livelihood diversifications and sustainability of the pastoralists under study. This shows the post drought coping and adaptive capacity for the pastoralists.

Table 2 Sources of income of the respondents

Sources of Income	Frequency	Percentage
Agriculture	25	16.04
Daily wage	12	7.69
Live stocks	110	70.51
Business trade	9	5.76

Total	156	100.00
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Source: Primary data 2020,

The majority of the respondents 110(70.51%) found that their main source of income comes through livestock at the same time less around 25(16.04%) depend upon agriculture and a few around 12(7.69%) do daily wages and iota around 9(5.76%) do some types of pretty business . This shows the majority people depend on livestock raring in the study area.

Housing pattern and Land holding pattern:

House and land both are important for human lives. Here the researcher has focused the housing pattern along with land holding pattern of the respondents in order to ascertain their socio-economic condition.

Table 3. Housing and Land holding pattern of the respondents

		frequency	percentage
Housing Pattern	Somali house (local house)	106	68.4%
	Buildings	50	31.6%
	Total	156	100%
Land holding Pattern		frequency	percentage
	Less than a hectare	76	49%
	About 1 hectare	23	14%
	No Land	57	37%
	Total	156	100%

Source: Primary data 2020,

This table shows majority 106(68.4%) of the respondents live in local house (Somali house) while 50(31.6%) live in permanent house that shows the majority people live in Somali house in

the study area. At the same time the majority 76(49.0%) of the respondents were found holding land less than a hectare, less around 23(14%) found holding 1 hector of land, and more 57(37%) found no land . This shows the majority people are holding very meager land in the study area.

Livestock holding of the respondents

The total unit of the livestock on the household of Degahbour district is summarized in Table below Pastoralists in the study area owned different class (diversified) of livestock species that includes Goat, Sheeps, Cattle and Poultry. The present finding supports the previous literatures, Scoones (1995) and Nigatu *et al.* (2004) reported that diversified livestock species or keeping mixed stock is common among pastoralists. During the focus group discussion, the participants stated that, diversifying of livestock species is due to that of different species have different feeding habits and appropriate for better use of resources. The other reason of diversifying livestock species in pastoralists is that to cope with climate change, drought and disease outbreaks.

Table 4. Livestock holding pattern of the respondents

Species	Numbers	Percentage
Goats	30	19.23
Sheeps	55	35.25
Goats &Sheeps(Both)	15	9.61
Cattle	5	3.20
Poultry	5	3.20

Total	110	70.49
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Source: Primary data, 2020

This table indicates live stocks holding pattern of the respondents. The result indicates that the majority 55(35.25 %) of the respondents rare sheep and almost equal 5(3.20%) rare cattle and poultry that shows the majority people in the study area rare sheep.

Major Constraints to Livestock Production

Production of Livestock is a challenge for pastoral community during normal year also because of many issues but it becomes more challenge during drought years. Therefore Researcher has brought and analyze the data about the perception of difficulties for livestock production during normal and drought years as shown below:-

Table.5. Major Constraints to Livestock Production in Normal and Drought Year

Constraints	Normal Year	Drought Year
Water Scarcity	73.0	92.5
Livestock Diseases	80.5	94.4
Range Degradation	77.0	90.2
Feed Shortage	76.0	94.3
Lack of Market Outlet	73.0	76.4

Source: Primary data,2020

Table No.5 shows that pastoralists have their opinion that during drought years, they face many constraints for livestock production. As the majority respondents 94.4% believe that their livestock badly affected by diseases during drought years but during normal year 80.5 % of the respondents that livestock are affected by the diseases , at the same time majority respondents 94.3%, 92.5% believe about shortage of food and water scarcity are the main constraint of

production of livestock during drought years. These shows that the real livelihood challenges were faced by the people during drought years in the study area.

Perception about Drought:

Here it speaks about the idea of drought that carries by the respondents in the study area. It is most important to prepare in advance to fight against such natural calamities occur oftenly. Therefore researcher collected datas and analyzed accordingly :-

Table 6 Perception about recurrent droughts by the pastoralists

Pastoralist' Perception on:	Likert Scale in decreasing order					Total
	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	
1. Frequency of Drought increase	35(22.43)	110(70.51)	6(3.84)	2(1.28)	3(1.92)	156(100)
2. Unpredictable Rainfall	10(6.41)	105(67.30)	15(9.61)	12(7.69)	14(8.97)	156(100)
3. The cessation of rainfall become more unpredictable	9(5.76)	80(51.28)	40(25.64)	20(12.8)	7(4.48)	156(100)
4. Decreased Rainfall days	30(19.23)	91(58.33)	30(19.23)	4(2.56)	1(0.64)	156(100)
5. The intensity of rainfall Decreased	24(14%)	82(46%)	40(23%)	24(14%)	5(3%)	175(100%)
The occurrence of untimely rainfall increased	16(9%)	101(58%)	37(21%)	14(8%)	7(4%)	175(100%)

Here the above table indicates that 35(22.43%) respondents strongly agreed that drought frequency has increased at the same time very little around 2(1.28%) respondents disagreed it. Again perception for unpredictable rain where we see that majority respondents 105(67.30%) just agreed that and also majority 15(9.61%) becomes neutral i.e neither strongly agreed or disagreed. In the case of prediction of Sessional rainfalls though the majority 80(51.28%) respondents agreed that sessional rainfalls become more unpredictable but again in the disagreed

side the majority 20(12.8%) respondents disagreed that. This shows the mixed reaction among the people in the study area.

Herd Diversification:

Under conditions of environmental variability, an opportunistic stocking strategy requires, in addition to herd mobility, species diversification (cattle, goat, sheep, and camel) and emphasis on incentives on primary productivity. The type and quantity of feed resources available determine species diversification plan of the households. A household's motivations for primary productivity, such as potential of herd to produce immediate products that household members demand (such as milk) and the restocking capability (ability to reproduce in a short interval) are important elements in both production systems.

Table.7 Livestock Diversification of the respondents

No of Species	Pastoralists	Percentage
One Type	80	51.28
Two Types	56	35.89
Three Types	20	12.82
Total	156	100

Source: Primary data

The above table shows that the majority 80(51.28%) respondents holding one types of species, remaining 56(35.89%) holding two types and very less around 20(12.82%) holds three types of species particularly goats and sheep in order to cope up with drought.

4.7 Livestock Raiding

Livestock raiding has long been one of the strategies used by livestock owners to rebuild their herds after the occurrence of drought. Key informants indicate that it has a long history. It is common in the study area. In some literature, it appears as “politics of the gun” to express the extent of violence (Hendrickson, et. al., 1996). We have also understood that livestock raiding is

a practice used mostly at the time of environmental stress or when there is a need to rebuild the livestock resource lost due to drought. In certain cases it is considered as a cultural practice to demonstrate group strength.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

The results of this study reveal that recurrent droughts are permanent problems that pastoral communities of Ethiopia in general and Harshin Woreda in particular have to live with. Moreover, the findings of this study made it clear that common pool rangeland resources in the study area have become inadequate to support the livelihoods of marginal pastoral groups. The overall effect of the degrading production environment in the pastoral areas has been gradual deterioration of health conditions. Productivity of livestock are exacerbated by the breakdown of seasonal grazing patterns, scarcity of water, reduction in pasture availability and conflict over resource use. The resources such as grazing land are considered as common-property resources among the pastoralists, they are not exclusively communal that lead often conflicts among pastorals and also with agro-pastoral community in the study area. The different coping strategies employed by the pastorals are more of short-term responses and are largely aimed at redressing short-term acute needs. Thus, they should not be considered as stand-alone efforts in foreseeing and mitigating acute emergencies. Hence some of the coping strategies followed by the pastoralists and normal people create lot of confusions among them that lead to unrest and social insecurity among pastoralist in the study area. Likewise, some of the income generating activities such as selling milk and meat would increase vulnerability of communities to drought over longer period. Food insecurity remains critical stage when such catastrophic situations aroused. Therefore, they continue with the traditional practices like sharing of resources with each other or periodic mobility to other places. The results of this study point to the fact that it is imperative that emphasis is placed on adaptive strategies so as to lessen the magnitude and recurrence of future emergencies. Within the broader framework the researcher has certain important recommendations in order to formulate policies and programs as mentioned below:-

Recommendations

- To develop a sustainable approach linked with local –regional and central governments to increasing adaptive capacity and resilience
- To bring different stakeholders in order to make appropriate decision during need hours.
- To develop certain platform where pastoralists can share their experiences, knowledge, information and skills between communities, sectors, formal and customary institutions.
- To develop awareness campaign to educate the people how to handle the catastrophic situations using resources optimally.
- Intra drought and post-drought management issues need to be understood better in order to identify the gaps in action during drought and post drought, therefore, further research is appreciable in context of the study area for better policy option
- Short-term and long-term options to use optimally the natural resources may be open to each pastoral society in order to enhance indigenous capacity building and developing copying mechanisms.
- To focus more on employment diversification and long-term transformation approaches to different households taking into account their socio-economic background.
- To strengthen the institution's pillars in order perform the role of institutions effectively in the pre-post drought era.

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